

Thickness dependent thermoelectric characterization of 2D SnSe₂ on a micro-chip platform

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Abstract

Investigating the temperature dependence of the Seebeck coefficient in low-dimensional materials provides an effective means to uncover how crystallinity, size, and thickness influence thermoelectric performance. Such insights are crucial for advancing large-scale thermoelectric devices and Seebeck-based sensors. To enhance measurement precision and efficiency, we developed a microchip platform specifically tailored for accurate Seebeck coefficient measurements in low-dimensional systems. The chip accommodates a broad range of samples, including both polycrystalline thin films (chemically or physically deposited) and mechanically exfoliated two-dimensional (2D) crystals. It integrates micro-heaters, temperature sensors, and voltage electrodes, enabling the generation of controlled in-plane temperature gradients and the simultaneous measurement of the induced Seebeck voltage (ΔV). Finite-element simulations support the formation of stable and tuneable temperature differences across the chip.

To validate the platform, we first measured Bi₂Te₃-based thin films, obtaining Seebeck coefficients consistent with reported literature values, thereby confirming the accuracy and robustness of the setup. Subsequently, mechanically exfoliated crystalline SnSe₂ flakes were investigated. Their Seebeck coefficient exhibited clear dependencies on both thickness and temperature, the absolute value increasing from $-349 \pm 20 \mu\text{V/K}$ at 100 K to $-521 \pm 10 \mu\text{V/K}$ at 300 K in a 198-nm-thick sample. These findings highlight the strong influence of dimensionality on thermoelectric transport in SnSe₂. Overall, this work establishes a versatile platform for evaluating emerging 2D materials and their heterostructures, facilitating both fundamental research and the engineering of efficient 2D material-based thermoelectric devices.

1. Introduction

As the global demand for sustainable energy grows, thermoelectric (TE) materials have attracted considerable attention as candidates for a wide range of applications, including energy harvesting¹⁻³, solid-state cooling^{4,5}, and sensing applications⁶. By directly converting waste heat into electricity through the Seebeck effect, TE devices provide a clean, reliable, and maintenance-free power source. The thermoelectric figure of merit, $ZT = S^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot T \cdot k^{-1}$, is governed by the interplay of the Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical conductivity (σ), and thermal conductivity (k), T being the temperature. Despite steady progress, TE technology is continuously advancing and is well positioned to achieve an impact comparable to photovoltaics⁷, solar thermal⁸, and window power⁹ technologies.

Beyond large-scale thermoelectric materials, such as bulk SnSe¹⁰⁻¹², extensive studies have explored novel two-dimensional (2D) materials, including graphene^{13,14} and Transition Metal Dichalcogenides (TMDCs)^{15,16}, due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, layered atomic structure, outstanding mechanical properties, and highly tunable electrical and thermal characteristics^{17,18}. Previous studies have shown that 2D materials exhibit thickness-dependent thermal properties^{17,19,20}, offering a promising route to enhance the thermoelectric ZT through nano-structuring¹⁷. Collectively, these properties make 2D materials highly attractive for next-generation thermoelectric applications, with significant potential to contribute to clean energy technologies and the development of efficient, miniaturized thermoelectric devices.

However, characterizing the Seebeck coefficient of low-dimensional materials remains challenging. Conventional approaches typically involve transferring exfoliated flakes onto insulating substrates, followed by electrode deposition^{21,22}. These multistep nanofabrication processes can leave resist residues on the sample surface, potentially altering its intrinsic properties and compromising measurement accuracy²¹. Conventional micro-devices employing suspended membrane architectures face significant challenges when applied to 2D materials. The fragile nature of the supporting membranes, combined with their millimeter-scale footprint, complicates the transfer of microscopic flakes and reduces device yield^{23,24}.

To address these limitations, we have developed an integrated microchip platform that enables precise in-plane temperature gradient control and direct measurement of the Seebeck coefficient in both deposited films and transferred 2D materials. The chip incorporates independent micro-heaters, temperature sensors, and voltage electrodes, and is fully compatible with dry-transfer techniques for handling 2D materials. Finite-element simulations further validate its thermal gradient stability. We first establish the reliability of the platform by benchmarking it against n- and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin films and then apply it to systematically investigate the thickness- and temperature-dependent Seebeck response of crystalline SnSe₂ over a temperature range of 100 K to 300 K, confirming both its accuracy and versatility. This approach provides a practical and scalable pathway for thermoelectric characterization in low-dimensional systems like thin films or 2D materials, with potential to accelerate materials discovery and device-level development at the microscale.

2. Experimental

2.1 Device fabrication and sample preparation

Seebeck measurement chips were fabricated on SiO₂ (400 nm)/Si wafers using standard direct-write laser lithography (Dilase 250, KLOE). The integrated micro-heaters, temperature sensors, and electrodes consist of Ti (5 nm)/Au (95 nm) layers defined via electron-beam evaporation and a subsequent lift-off process. For calibration, n- and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin films were deposited onto the chips using magnetron sputtering. For 2D material measurements, bulk SnSe₂ crystals were mechanically exfoliated onto a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamp. Target flakes were then aligned and transferred onto the chip electrodes using a dry-transfer technique (Figure 1(c)). Flake thickness was preliminarily assessed by optical contrast and quantified by atomic force microscopy (AFM).

2.2 Electrical and thermoelectric measurement setup

Electrical connections between the chip and the measurement system were established via aluminum wire bonding. The on-chip temperature sensors were calibrated by performing four-probe resistance measurements of the Au lines, exploiting the linear temperature dependence of gold resistivity. A Keithley DMM 6500 digital multimeter was used to record the Seebeck voltage (ΔV), while heater currents were supplied by a programmable DC source (AOIP 8310). For temperature-dependent measurements, the chip was mounted in a closed-cycle cryostat under vacuum. The global substrate temperature was controlled using a resistive heater and monitored with a commercial Pt-100 sensor placed adjacent to the chip. To generate in-plane temperature difference, one of the on-chip micro-heaters was powered by a direct current, while the integrated Au sensors monitored the resulting temperature difference across the flake.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1(a) presents the integrated microchip platform developed for Seebeck coefficient measurements. A micro-heater located on one side of the device establishes an in-plane temperature difference (ΔT), while two Au electrodes detect the resulting thermoelectric voltage across a 100 μm channel. The mechanically exfoliated SnSe₂ flakes placed on the device were first characterized using Raman spectroscopy (Horiba T64000), with the spectra (Figure 1(b)) confirming their crystalline nature¹⁹.

The complete measurement circuit is depicted in Figure 1(c). The device, fabricated on a SiO₂ (400 nm)/Si substrate, incorporates two micro-heaters (Heater-L and heater-R), two independent four-probe temperature sensors (Temperature sensor-L and Temperature sensor-R), and electrodes dedicated to both resistance and ΔV measurements. The temperature sensors were strategically aligned parallel to the Seebeck electrodes to ensure that both voltage and thermal gradients were measured along the same axis, thereby minimizing geometric artifacts. The heater resistance was approximately 1200 Ω , providing stable Joule heating under moderate DC bias. The gold temperature sensors, with resistance values around 28 Ω , functioned as resistive thermometers; their calibration against substrate temperature confirmed linear resistance–temperature behaviour over the temperature range of 100 – 300 K.

Figure 1. Integrated microchip platform for Seebeck coefficient measurements in low-dimensional materials. (a) Schematic of the in-plane heat flow and temperature difference generation on the chip for Seebeck characterization of layered SnSe₂. (b) Raman spectra of a typical layered SnSe₂ thin film. (c) Circuit design of the Seebeck measurement chip, incorporating micro-heaters, temperature sensors, and voltage electrodes. The red dashed box indicates the designated region for sample placement. (d) Optical images of the measurement chip featuring a dry-transferred SnSe₂ flake and a sputtered n-type Bi₂Te₃ film (insets: enlarged views), scale bar, 100 μm.

Figure 1(d) shows optical micrographs of the chip, highlighting both the dry-transferred SnSe₂ flake and the sputtered Bi₂Te₃ film. In both cases, excellent adhesion to the underlying prefabricated Au electrodes and SiO₂/Si substrate was observed via Scanning Electron Microscope, revealing intimate contact between the SiO₂ thin film and the 2D films that ensures low thermal and electrical contact resistances. Consequently, the temperature difference derived from the Au resistance sensors is taken to be equivalent to the in-plane gradient across the sample. To quantitatively validate this assumption, we compare the vertical thermal resistance at the interface between the SnSe₂ flake and the Au electrode to the in-plane one. With a typical Thermal Boundary Resistance (TBR) for metal/2D interfaces of $R_{\text{TBR}} \approx 5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} / \text{W}$ ²⁵ and our large contact area of 500 μm², we estimate the total vertical resistance to be on the order of $R_{\text{vertical}} \approx 100 \text{ K/W}$. This number has to be compared to the in-plane thermal resistance ($R_{\text{in-plane}}$) of the SnSe₂. Assuming an in-plane thermal conductivity of $k_{\text{in-plane}} \approx 6 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$ ²⁶, a channel length of $L = 100 \text{ μm}$, the width $w = 100 \text{ μm}$

and a conservative upper bound for the flake thickness of 200nm, the in-plane thermal resistance of SnSe₂ is on the order of $R_{\text{in-plane}} \approx 10^6$ K/W much more resistive than the contact thermal resistance justifying our hypothesis. This optimized device architecture successfully enabled reproducible generation and monitoring of in-plane temperature difference, thereby allowing accurate extraction of the Seebeck coefficient in both layered SnSe₂ and reference Bi₂Te₃ thin films.

Local ΔT induced by the on-chip heaters was measured by the integrated gold sensors. Devices were pre-conditioned by liquid-nitrogen thermal cycling to stabilize Au film resistivity^{27,28}. Both on-chip temperature sensors were calibrated against the substrate temperature using a commercial Pt-100 temperature sensor, and they exhibited a gradual increase in resistance with temperature (Figure 2(b)). Minor differences in their slopes were attributed to dimensional variations and were employed to evaluate the temperature difference during measurements. During Seebeck characterization, a one-sided heating current generated a stable temperature difference across the chip, and the ΔT between the two sensors was recorded, as shown in Figure 2(c). In the measurement (Figure 2(c–d)), a stepwise increase in the heater current caused incremental rises in both ΔT and ΔV . A linear relationship between ΔV and ΔT was observed, with the slope corresponding to the negative Seebeck coefficient ($S = -\Delta V/\Delta T$). The negative sign arises from the measurement convention where the positive electrode is connected to the hot side. Within the temperature range of 285–300 K, the Seebeck coefficient of a 12 nm thick crystalline n-type SnSe₂ flake was -408 ± 1 $\mu\text{V/K}$. The temperature-dependent resistance of crystalline SnSe₂ was measured as the substrate temperature was varied (Figure 2(e)).

To further validate the measurement technique, a COMSOL simulation model was developed, as shown in Figure 3(a). The chip was heated up via the left side heater, and the resulting temperature profile along the blue dashed line in Figure 3(a) is depicted in Figure 3(b). The temperature gradually decreases from the heater region on the left to the right side of the chip. The simulated ΔT between the two Seebeck measurement electrodes was extracted directly from this profile. To evaluate the influence of cryostat's ambient temperature on ΔT , simulations were performed at temperatures ranging from 100 K to 300 K under constant heating power, as shown in Figure 3(c). The results in Figure 3(d) show that ΔT increases with both chip temperature and heating power. This behavior is attributed to the temperature-dependent thermal conductivity of silicon^{30,31}. In the 100 to 300 K range, the decreasing thermal conductivity of silicon limits thermal dissipation, causing more pronounced localized heating near the heater. This effect, analogous to increasing heating power, leads to a higher ΔT . The results demonstrate that the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity must be considered when designing thermoelectric experiments, especially when selecting the substrate material.

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Figure 2. Electrical and Seebeck characterization of the crystalline SnSe₂ flake. (a) Temperature calibration of both temperature sensors in the 100 to 300 K range. (b) Temperature comparison between the two temperature sensors over the sampling points, with one point recorded approximately every second. (c-d) Stepwise increase in heating current to generate an increased ΔT across the 12 nm thick SnSe₂ flake: (c) Evolution of the temperature difference over sampling points, (d) Corresponding ΔV over sampling points after subtraction of a 6.713 mV baseline offset at $\Delta T = 0$ (being 6.820mV at 80 K), attributed to offset in the thermoelectric voltage at electrode contacts and cryostat leads. This offset value unique for each base temperature, is calibrated and removed to obtain the Seebeck voltage of the sample. (e) Linear relationship between ΔT and ΔV measured at a substrate temperature of

300K, and the slope of the fitted line yields the Seebeck coefficient of the flake. (f) Electrical resistance of the SnSe₂ thin film.

Figure 3. Simulation of thermal transport in the Seebeck measurement chip. (a) COMSOL Multiphysics simulation model was built based on the Seebeck measurement chip, where heating is applied via the left-side heater (Heater-L). (b) Simulated temperature profile along the dashed line in (a), showing a temperature decreases from the heated region, toward the opposite side. The extracted ΔT represents the temperature difference between the two Seebeck measurement electrodes. (c) Effect of ambient temperature on ΔT at constant heating power, demonstrating an increase in temperature difference with substrate temperature, as shown in figure (d). (d) Extracted simulated ΔT increases as a function of temperature for the on-chip heating power of 100, 80 and 60 mW.

A complete set of measurements was taken across the entire temperature range of 100 - 300 K. Both ΔV and ΔT were simultaneously recorded and found to increase with temperature, consistent with the expected thermoelectric response (Figure 4(a) and (b)). The observed increase in ΔT agrees well with of COMSOL simulations, further confirming the accuracy of the measurement platform. However, at low temperatures, both ΔV and ΔT exhibit larger relative uncertainties, due to weaker signals and elevated signal ratio. The relative uncertainty in the Seebeck coefficient, was quantified via standard error propagation, approximating the quadrature sum of the relative uncertainties in ΔV and ΔT ; these uncertainties are calculated as the fluctuation of individual data points relative to the total signal value from repeated

measurements. This temperature-dependent uncertainty decreases from 16% at 100K to 6% at 295K, as shown in Figure 4(c), with the total uncertainty (red) dominated by ΔT contributions (black) at low temperature owing to its limited magnitude.

Figure 4. Temperature-dependent Seebeck coefficients of layered SnSe₂ and Bi₂Te₃ thin films. (a, b) ΔV and ΔT as functions of substrate temperature (100-300 K) at fixed heating currents of 7, 8, and 9 mA, showing increases with temperature, lines are guides for the eyes. (c) Temperature-dependent relative uncertainties in Seebeck coefficient measurements: uncertainty in Seebeck coefficient (red triangles), relative uncertainty in Temperature (Black squares), and relative uncertainty in Voltage (blue circles). (d) Temperature-dependent Seebeck coefficients for crystalline SnSe₂ flakes (198 nm and 12 nm) and both n- and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin films.

Both n-type and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin films were first characterized to benchmark the measurement platform, with their Seebeck coefficients shown in Figure 4(d). At 300 K, n- and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin film exhibit values of $-92 \pm 10 \mu\text{V/K}$ and $+246 \pm 10 \mu\text{V/K}$, respectively, with minimal temperature dependence. These results are consistent with previously reported literature values³, thereby validating the accuracy and reliability of the thermoelectric measurement platform. Building on this validation, we investigated layered SnSe₂. The Seebeck coefficient exhibits clear dependencies on both temperature and thickness. For a 198-nm-thick sample, the absolute value of the coefficient increases from $-349 \pm 20 \mu\text{V/K}$ at 100 K to $-521 \pm 10 \mu\text{V/K}$ at 300 K, showing similar temperature-dependent Seebeck behavior to Bridgman-method-grown single-crystal SnSe₂³². In contrast, a 12-nm-thick flake shows a greater increase,

rising from $-175 \pm 20 \mu\text{V/K}$ to $-412 \pm 30 \mu\text{V/K}$ over the same range. These observations confirm that both the temperature and thickness strongly affect Seebeck response in layered SnSe₂. The increase in Seebeck coefficient with temperature is attributed to the interplay between carrier concentration and the energy dependence of transport properties. As shown in Figure 2a, the temperature-dependent resistance of layered SnSe₂ correlates with the rising Seebeck coefficient, consistent with behaviour observed in single-crystal SnSe₂ synthesized via the chemical transport method³³. Electrical resistance in SnSe₂ flakes decreases with thickness (for example, from 22.82 k Ω at 12 nm to 3.07 k Ω at 198 nm, measured at 300 K, 100 nm channel, with a contact resistance measured with a standard 4-probe technique that remain stable around 250 Ω), yet thicker flakes exhibit higher Seebeck coefficients ($|S|$ from 412 $\mu\text{V/K}$ at 12 nm to 521 $\mu\text{V/K}$ at 198 nm). The bulk resistivity σ drops from $7.3 \times 10^3 \text{ S/m}$ (12 nm) to $3.0 \times 10^3 \text{ S/m}$ (198 nm)³⁴.

4. Conclusion

We developed a microchip specifically designed for precise characterization of the Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity in low-dimensional materials. The design enables direct material transfer or deposition, allowing simultaneous measurement of the temperature difference and Seebeck voltage, thereby eliminating complex fabrication steps and enhancing measurement consistency. Benchmarking with n- and n-type Bi₂Te₃-based thin film yielded results consistent with literature values, confirming the platform's reliability.

Using this platform, we demonstrated that the Seebeck coefficient of layered SnSe₂ strongly depends on temperature and thickness, reflecting intrinsic thermoelectric transport behaviour in low-dimensional systems. Notably, a Seebeck coefficient of $-521 \pm 10 \mu\text{V/K}$ was achieved at room temperature, highlighting the strong potential of SnSe₂ for thermoelectric applications. COMSOL Multiphysics simulations further supported the accuracy of the temperature gradient analysis. Validating the robustness of the platform. Beyond Seebeck coefficient characterization, the microchip platform could be extended to the power factor measurement by adding a four probe measurement setup holds promise for further thermoelectric investigations, such as tuning thermoelectric performance via phononic crystal engineering and surface chemical modification. These capabilities pave the way for advances in thermoelectric applications and the development of more efficient energy-harvesting materials.

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